

Why Switch to Direct Primary Care?

The new [Direct Primary Care practice](#) cuts out all the intermediaries and nurtures a direct, genuine relationship between doctor and patient. For an affordable monthly subscription fee that can cost anywhere between \$30-\$300 per month, patients get 24/7 access to their general practice doctor via their personal line.

It's true, your [Direct Primary Care](#) subscription does not replace your health insurance, but here's a major perk you'll be thrilled to hear: having a Direct Primary Care subscription covers everything with regard to routine and preventive care.

This means you get to reduce your insurance premiums to a more affordable one which covers hospitalization services, subspecialty, and surgical expenses only.

With a [Direct Primary Care subscription](#), the chances of getting hospitalized are also much lower because you have a Direct Primary Care physician who is committed to disease prevention, early diagnosis, and overall comprehensive care management.

Join the movement for better health care and find a Direct Primary Care physician at FindMyDirectDoctor.com